

Manuscripts Digital documentation Using Decorative Bookbinding for Dating Medieval Manuscripts

Applied aspects to a group of Medieval manuscript covers

by
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SUMMARY

The need to protect cultural property from damage, loss, theft, and crimes against humanity served as a catalyst for the development of documentation practices. Medieval manuscripts are among the most interesting areas of documentation.

This material provides a window into history from the 5th to early 16th centuries, unfortunately, while the manuscripts themselves were studied, the links were only noted briefly and when the latter looked for more information, the links themselves were destroyed.

Therefore, the research discusses how to lay a basis for documenting the icons and inscriptions engraved on the covers of manuscripts that may carry connotations and symbols that contribute to determining the date and type of subject matter of the manuscript's content.

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Chapter I: Introduction

Introduction

Documentation is a core activity of the Museum, the role of documentation in the Museum is to ensure efficient recording of, and access to, collections information, meeting international standards of good collections stewardship, security, accountability, study, research, use and access.

Manuscripts as a documentary Cultural heritage are often subject to digitization processes resulting in image material, even for textual contents. It is therefore common, in case of valuable Manuscript's collections, to have descriptive information generated by the institutions, along with digitized images, transcriptions created by scholars, translations and even miscellaneous annotations is necessary.

But manuscripts also are difficult targets document the priority always for poor conservation conditions collections, and especially those collection that demonstrate a sophisticated visual and technical artistic quality and reflect a rich intellectual and scholarly tradition, and cover a diverse range of topics and genres, including:

- The natural and physical sciences (astronomy, mathematics, botany, and medicine);
- The literary arts (poetic verse, panegyric texts about holy priests, families or, grammars);
- Christian religious sciences such as theology, jurisprudence and legal opinions; and historical accounts

The Documentation Policy supports the Museum's mission and strategic priorities, as the purpose of the Documentation Policy is to provide the framework within which the Museum formulates and implements a Documentation Plan, guiding the Museum in how it documents its collections.

Medieval manuscript codices are important historical documents, often also important art they represent superior base for the understanding of the book structure as such and represent very important source for codicological and conservation studies of medieval binding.

Research Problem

Unfortunately, despite the fact that the manuscripts are important subject of study, but the covers were referred to in a simple and only for a short period and when searching to obtain more information, we find that some of the covers were damaged or replaced with new covers that does not hold any historical evidence to the manuscript.

Even the idea of digitization, which has spread significantly in most museums, did not demonstrate the required satisfaction in digitizing the covers, especially that some covers carry carved motifs and icons that need precise operations from digital photography to clarify them and link their history to the history of the manuscript.

During the conservation process, the conservator also faces the problem of deciding whether the cover is the original cover of the manuscript or was attached to it in a previous restoration process? and should he retrieve the cover on the manuscript or attach it and replaced with a new cover?

Therefore, the process of accurate documentation of the manuscript covers and the information they carry (floral ornaments - geometrical ornaments - icons - or even texts) is a very important process for documenting the history of the manuscript and the time period it belongs to.

Objectives of the Research

Documenting all the information related to the manuscript Cover is one of the most important stages in identifying the manuscript history, documenting all the changes that occurred to it before or after the conservation process.

The objectives of manuscripts covers digital documentation can be summarized in :

- Provide an historic archive about manuscripts covers they can be used to maintain information about the production, collection, ownership, and use of manuscripts and information about the date of manuscript and date of the cover itself.
- Recording all information that can be obtained from visual documentation of the covers (motifs - icons - texts) to provide a descriptive catalog for cover features to help in manuscripts dating.

- Using digital software (Adobe Photoshop - Adobe Illustrator) to extract the visual information needed for documentation.
- Collecting Metadata (descriptive data, technical data, administrative data, image quality data) for a fine indexing of the cover and the description of the cover contents and date.

Trying to adapt all the ICT facilities and (digitization, visualization, documentary software) to provide digital information service that allow the possibility of displaying a selection of the cultural heritage materials and make all the results available to a scholarly audience, is critically important, just as important as conservation and cataloguing efforts. But this raises many questions:

- For whom may this information really be interesting?
- Are researchers ready to change the old documentation methods and pay attention to the new aspect presented by the research?
- Would it be worth the Visualization and digitization cost?
- Would it be used within conservation labs or Manuscripts Museums or both?
- What is the level of ICT for documenters or restorers who are likely to use the documentation methods observed in the research?

Chapter II: Literature Review

Digital information

Digital resources have greatly changed the way in which libraries function as information centers. With the transformation from traditional print collections into versatile electronic resources, information including full text, can now be accessed everywhere 24 hours a day.

Museums will have to accommodate the need for both a traditional experience and a digital and technological experience, Museums must invent new ways to tell stories of the object. They must engage actual visitors in the creation and curation of content, the move towards digital also has significant implications on how content is sourced, displayed and explored. Many museums already make use of technologies such as tablets and social media. (c., Egypt, September 2019.)

The growth of digital services is not only transforming our interaction with the digital world but increasingly shaping our understanding of how handle and care for the collections through improving and enhancing new software and auxiliary programs to help us understanding manuscripts conservation as a domain and encourage multidisciplinary for engagement and impact to make sure that, it is available for everyone, it will be valued by people in the future by estimating the mass and depth of damage and find the proper conservation required. (c., Egypt, September 2019.) (Matjia Strlic, 2019)

Digital information and cultural heritage

A digital information is a facility in which collections are managed in digital formats (as opposed to print, microform or any other media) and are accessible by computer. The digital content may be stored locally or remotely and accessed remotely via computer networks.

The digital content may be stored locally or accessed remotely via computer networks. In a brief, digital information is one in which a significant proportion of resources is available in machine readable formats as opposed to print or microform and is accessible by means of computers (Namande)

The aim of digital documentation is long-term, error-free storage of digital information, with the means of retrieval and interpretation, for the period that information is required. (Chhatwal, 2009)

Cultural heritage is a term that refers to tangible cultural heritage such as ruins, temples and buildings, digital preservation is the management of digital information over time. It takes the form of processes and activities that ensure continued access to information and all kinds of records, both scientific and cultural heritage, that exist in digital form.

Under the term ‘cultural heritage resources’ we sort all resources that are represented in libraries, archives and museums and are of cultural or historical value. This definition covers tangible goods like Manuscripts, writs, pictures or statues as well as music or films. A ‘cultural heritage system’ consists of several digitized cultural heritage resources about a special topic which are represented with their contexts to a public audience. (Singh, 2012)

Providing information in a computer format that is standardized, organized and available on demand from common system. Documentary heritage as Manuscript collections are converted into compressed digital formats with specialized digital cameras and stored systematically for future reference. The digitization of manuscripts and other Documentary cultural heritage resources is needed for the many reasons we concern with the following (Namande) (Singh, 2012)

Multiple access to information. The same resources can be used simultaneously by several institutions and patrons. Digital libraries provide a faster method of accessing and exchanging information in all sectors such as research, scholarship, medicine, government services and business.

Resource sharing. Digital information can easily be shared and therefore is available to everybody, as opposed to conventional information materials which require expensive duplication of material in order to meet the needs of many users.

Systems sustainability. Digital systems to support documentation promote sustainability and ensure that they can be maintained into the future. Also, use of open source and standard technologies where appropriate, and proprietary solutions.

Added value. Certain characteristics of objects, primarily the quality of images, may be improved. Digitization can enhance legibility and remove visible flaws such as stains and discoloration it also may through advanced techniques from digital imaging, to extract hidden information that may contribute to setting a specific date or adding a scientific or literary value to the object, and this point is the core of this research.

Manuscripts as a documentary Cultural heritage are often subject to digitization processes resulting in image material, even for textual contents. It is therefore common, in case of valuable Manuscripts collections, to have digital documentation alongside with the descriptive information generated by the institutions, transcriptions created by scholars, translations and even miscellaneous annotations is necessary, and to convert Manuscripts as archival materials into a digital format, all available methods to capture high-quality, well calibrated images should be considered. (B., 2012-2014)

Manuscripts as a Cultural heritage

What is a Manuscript?

Etymologically, manuscript means something that is handwritten. Here the term manuscript is related to antiquity not necessarily means the write up submitted by an author to a publisher. The Antiquities and Art Treasures Act, 1972 lays down the legal framework for custody of manuscripts. Antiquities, defined under the Act include “any manuscript, record or other document which is of scientific, historical, literary or aesthetic value and which has been in existence for not less than seventy-five years.” If this definition is taken into consideration in phase value, a manuscript means

" a hand-written document which has scientific, historical, literary or aesthetic value and which is at least seventy-five-year-old" (Dr. Ramesh C Gaur, 2009)

Bookbinding Art and History

In ancient Mediterranean times a roll (leather or papyrus) was the common method of recording written language. These rolls would be unrolled for reading and then rolled back up for storage.

A Codex by contrast is that it is formed of folded writing surfaces, parchment (leather) papyrus or later paper. Each sheet is folded once only, makes two leaves or four pages, joined at the fold, a number of sheets stacked together and folded then makes a quire (gathering of leaves).

A codex consists of one or more such quires and is not necessarily sewn. It is then easy to see how the codex was then progressed to be sewn to keep the pages/leaves in order, because if you dropped the quire your pages could all fall apart and out of order. A thread passing thru the fold of the quire acts to keep the pages in order and together. In one of the simplest forms this can be known as pamphlet stitch which was quite common once the printing revolution occurred and printed materials were getting distributed regularly. If you had more than one quire then the separate quires needed to be sewn together to keep everything in order.

A cover may then be attached/wrapped around the codex to help protect it, at which point we now have a Binding (Winter, 2011)

The emergence of Christianity was one of the most important factors that led to the emergence of the book form in "codex form" and dispensing of the scrolls, where the emergence of the codex linked to the popularity of Christianity and the need to copy the Bible Scriptures and the Codex form appeared for the first time with the emergence of the Bible.

Nag Hammadi first codices

Although leaves or fragments of leaves of the earliest codices can be traced back to the second century AD, the first surviving binding structures seem to date only from the third/fourth century AD. The best-known examples are the Gnostic manuscripts found in 1945, buried in a jar near the Egyptian Village of Nag Hammadi, close to the ancient monastery of Chenoboskion, and comprising 13 papyrus codices still in their original leather binding.

The covers are made of prepared goatskin or sheepskin, the upper covers have flaps similar to those later routine on Islamic bindings extending over the fore-edge and folding around to the lower cover. Leather thongs are attached to the flaps, by means of which the volumes could be wrapped up and tied. Some of the volumes also have remains of thongs on the top and bottom of the covers.

The covers are more than simply wrappers, for their insides are lined with papyrus cartonnage, built up into boards over which the turn-ins of the covers were folded and glued or tied. To secure the quire in its cover, two pairs of holes were stabbed through the fold of the leaves, one pair toward the top, the other toward the bottom. A leather thong was passed through each pair, and then either through the spine of the cover itself or through a strip of leather guard, and its ends tied together. If leather guards were used, they were glued to the inside of the covers, so that in either case the codex was attached to the cover. Several of the bindings are decorated, the most elaborate scribed with fillets dividing them into cross and X patterns.

Unfortunately, while the codices themselves were studied the bindings were only briefly noted and when latter looked at to get more information the bindings themselves had been destroyed.

Parchment bookbinding

The use of parchment for the book itself and of wood for the covers had been introduced to the north of the Mediterranean not only by technical requirements but for reasons of trade and politics. The Arab conquest of Egypt in the seventh century severed that country from the cultural realm of Byzantium. From about 750AD the Arabs knew how to make paper and neglected the cultivation of papyrus.

Having no longer direct access to this source and paper being still unknown, the countries of the west reverted to costlier parchment or vellum. It was better suited to the European climate and did more to satisfy the new pride in a book's appearance.

Since parchment tends to curl unless under firm pressure, heavy wooden covers were needed to replace the Egyptian pasteboard (made from papyrus), and this in its turn affected the development of Western bindings. (Winter, 2011)

With the spread of Christianity, the art of book binding spread in all countries of the Roman Empire, the demand for copying and binding increased, and the art of binding decoration developed and diversified according to topics and genres, including Christian religious sciences such as theology, jurisprudence and legal opinions; and historical accounts. (Ibrahim, 2006)

Medieval Manuscript

One of the most interesting areas for documentation is Medieval manuscripts. This material offers a window into history from the 5th to early 16th century, It began with the fall of the Western Roman Empire and merged into the Renaissance manuscript, Medieval codices are important historical documents, often also important art they represent superior base for the understanding of the book structure as such and represent very important source for codicological and conservation studies of medieval binding, as far as the bookbinding technique is concerned, the Medieval bindings represents quite literally a precise continuation of the Greek-style technique with signs of influence from the west mostly in the decoration of the bindings, Greek-style binding remained essentially unchanged. In structure and to a large extent in decoration throughout the Middle Ages until the sixteenth century until the seventeenth century in various cases. Thus, in the broadest sense of the term, many of the bindings considered medieval in descent.

Post-Byzantine is generally designated the era between the fall of Constantinople to the Ottomans (and the consequent end of the Byzantine empire) in 1453 and the nineteenth century with the formation of the modern Greek state. It is used as a general term in order to designate the culture of Christian-Orthodox populations, predominantly Greek-speaking, living under the rule of the Ottomans, Venetian etc in areas of the Eastern Europe, the Balkans and the Eastern Mediterranean, mostly parts of the former Byzantine Empire or its network of influences. These populations continued the Byzantine tradition in fields like art, architecture, literature etc, though with strong influences both from Western Europe and the Ottoman East.

In the specific context of bindings, the term post-Byzantine is used in its chronological, historical, and geographical sense without the intention of giving it any typological meaning, apart from the possible implication that it refers to binding structures that may present a great variation depending on the specific location and time they have been produced. These can vary from « full » Greek-style bindings to « full » Western European, or Islamic bindings, with many variations in between. The term also offers relative flexibility in describing more specific groups of bindings. For example, we can talk about « Greek-style post- Byzantine bindings », « western style post-Byzantine bindings », « Islamic style post-Byzantine bindings », etc. (Boudalis, 2002) (Evans., spring,2001)

Below we show some of the features of binding and its development in this period, which during this research we are working to document selected models of manuscripts' covers belongs to this period

6th – 9th centuries

- Western book blocks were of papyrus or vellum/parchment.
- Wood or papyrus boards were chisel trimmed flush to the text. Boards and text were attached by the sewing threads forming Byzantine bindings

9th – 14th centuries

- Board attachment generally consisted of a raised thong through a tunnel to the surface of the board. A hole allowed the thong to go through to the inside where it was pegged with a wooden peg.
- By the 10th century bind tooling with individual tools was in use regularly (had been seen as early as 4th century Nag Hammadi codex's)

12th century

The 12th century is the earliest period for which there are several hundred bindings in existence making it possible to generalize with some confidence.

- The spine was still flat.
- Wooden boards were still in use.
- Cover decorating techniques included blind tooling, inking in, painting, and piercing. Board clasps were plaited thong with loops and bond pegs.

13th – 14th centuries

- Leather braid headbands appear.
- Wooden boards were still trimmed flush to the text block.
- Clasps were often two straps with the clasp attached to the foreedge.
- Panel stamps were introduced in the Netherlands and were in use in England by 1480.
- 13th century Islamic binding incorporated gold.

- The earliest known English textile binding is an embroidered canvas cover showing the Annunciation and crucifixion.

15th century

The many changes in the 15th and 16th centuries were largely related to the onset of the commercial pressures which continued through to the present day. Most changes have involved speeding up of techniques and introduction of cheaper materials (non archival), Binders were still usually working on one book at a time, completing the whole thing in one sequence.

- Pasteboard boards (paper sheets pasted together) largely replaced wooden boards.
- Lacing- in holes were usually on the diagonal, adjusting tensioning to the use of pasteboards.
- Board squares were introduced replacing boards cut flush to the text block. Chamfering of the text block became uncommon. Boards were trimmed separately from the text block using the plough.
- High quality full-thickness leather and vellum were in use, with consideration given to the matching of materials to the weight and size of the text block and to the use to which the book would be put.
- The adhered spine covering was often of Morocco leather.
- By the 15th century the position of clasps frequently indicated the country of origin: English and French clasps were on the upper board and catch on the lower, in Italy, the Netherlands, and Germany clasps were generally on the lower board and catch on the upper.
- Gold tooling was imported from the east and was in use in Italy about 1470. Hot tools were used for gilding. The roll (fillet) was introduced to replace individual tools for straight lines or lines of ornament.
- Edge gilding was introduced in some areas.
- There was logic to the progressions seen at this time; the use of paste-boards led to diagonal hole placement for tight lacing, paper text blocks led to the recessing of sewing cords, to rounding, and smooth spines. All of this allowed for attached covers.
- The use of clasps declined. They did not attach firmly to paste boards and were less necessary with paper text blocks than they were for vellum text blocks, which required confinement.

(Winter, 2011)

Early 16th century

By the beginning of the 16th century the heavy, wooden-boarded folios were being supplanted by leather bound octavos with gold tooled decoration. The earlier books were intended to be stored flat or chained to lecterns whereas the smaller, more compact 'humanist' 16th century bindings were intended to be portable and moveable.

From the 16th century on, commercial pressure required speeding up of technique, smaller sizes of books in larger editions, pre-made or precut components, introduction of inexpensive covering materials

- By the end of the 16th century glued on headbands were introduced.
- Gold tooling was predominant, starting in France in 1520.
- Deerskin and other leathers fall out of normal use after the fifteenth century.
- Goatskin first used in English bookbinding in the 1540's
- Embroidered bindings can be found throughout the sixteenth century, often depicting religious imagery or plants, landscapes, or other possibilities.

Bindings made before 1530 in England are likely to have wooden boards; between 1530 and 1570 boards or pasteboards (2-4mm) may be found, but more often wood. After 1570 wood is unusual and after 1600 is rarely found, this practice was imported from the Middle east where pasteboard had been used for bindings for several centuries.

Bookbinding ornamental fashion

The progression of binding fashions like ornamental fashion can generally be thought of as a wave-like process, rippling across Europe. Ideas started in one place and spread outwards. English decorative styles were particularly influenced by binding practices on the other side of the English Channel, in France and the Low countries, but they in turn were often influenced by trends set further south.

Arabesque centerpiece blocks, for example, started life as a design idea in the medieval Islamic world, and entered the European ornamental vocabulary via the Italian trading ports around the end of the fifteenth century. By the end of the sixteenth century, centerpieces were being used

right across Europe, from Spain to Russia, taking in England and Denmark as well as Germany and Bohemia. (Winter, 2011)

also, some historic bindings held other kinds of evidence about their previous ownership and use. They used to be stamped with the names, initials, or armorial bearings of former owners, and they may carry library markings showing how and where they were once stored. They may contain within them fragments of other books, used as endleaves, spine linings, or other structural strengthening devices. In an age when plain paper was relatively expensive, it was common practice to cut up discarded vellum and paper books or documents for this purpose, and many bindings, particularly of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, contain such fragments. Countless medieval manuscripts were subjected to this treatment, and all kinds of very rare items, such as fifteenth-century printed ephemera and Anglo-Saxon manuscripts are known about only through snippets surviving as binders' waste. (Boudalis, 2002)

Presentation of the collections

The selected models for the application are from the collection of manuscripts of the Greek Orthodox Patriarchate of medieval manuscripts, for the variety of topics and methods of their binding and

abound in different medieval art, a group of the collection was conserved in the manuscript's restoration laboratory affiliate manuscript's museum at the Library of Alexandria through the period of 2012 till 2020.

The manuscript models in this research were selected according to the variety of decorative topics on the covers, which allows a wider space for research and documentation. The manuscripts' ages are limited between the fifteenth and seventeenth centuries.

From the visual observation we found the four manuscripts are covered with a leather of medium thickness, probably of goat based on visual observation, and colors are various hues of brown, three manuscripts are covered in wooden boards, one manuscript has a paste-board cover.

The four leather covers of the manuscripts are decorated with blind tooling, the decoration between the left and right board differs, the number of tools used to decorate the two boards between 4 and 5 tools.

Chapter III: Methodology

Objectives of Documentation Process

The need to protect cultural property against damage, loss, theft, and crimes against humanity has acted as an incentive to the development of standardized documentation practices. The 1970 UNESCO Convention on the means of prohibiting and preventing the illicit import, export, and transfer of ownership of cultural property recommends that national inventories be established to identify cultural property. (Alice Grant, First published June 1995 in printed and electronic forms.)

The availability of good documentation also ensures that knowledge about objects extends beyond the objects themselves. It provides a foundation for the use of a collection by curators, researchers, and the public according to the following Objectives of documentation:

- Ensure accountability for objects: they can be used to define the objects that are owned by a museum, identify the objects, and record their location.
- Aid the security of objects: they can be used to maintain information about the status of objects and provide descriptions and evidence of ownership in the event of theft.
- Provide an historic archive about objects: they can be used to maintain information about the production, collection, ownership, and use of objects and as a means of protecting the long-term value of data.
- Support physical and intellectual access to objects: they can be used to support access to objects themselves and information about the objects.
- Recording the damage before restoration and clarifying the restoration work carried out after the restoration.
- Protect the restorer from any accusation of damage in the absence of the purpose to be restored in custody.
- Preserve the right of the Foundation to retain its property.

Documentation Process

The initial stage in recording the cover data and the inscriptions on it was by using the primitive method of tracing the inscription using paper and a thick pencil to transfer the straight lines.

The initial form of the inscription or drawing was extracted under the magnifying glass as a prelude to infer the forms resulting from the photographic process and to determine whether the inscriptions on the cover were of importance or historical significance worthy of documentation and help in dating the manuscript or not.

1The process of extracting the initial shape of the engraving and drawing under the magnifying glass

Documentary Photography

Imaging setup.

The camera is fixed on a copy stand Beseler CS-14 Copy stand facing vertically downwards. Four tungsten-halogen lamps illuminate the sample at an angle of 45°.

A copy stand is a device used to facilitate the photography of large flat objects like artwork, books, or manuscripts. Copy stands are used in archiving, artwork reproduction, forensics and many more fields or arts and sciences. The typical photographic copy stand is comprised of a base board and a vertical column onto which the camera platform rides. (LensNotes, 2020)

2Model for Beseler CS-14 Copy stand

3While photographing one of the manuscripts on a Beseler CS-14 Copy stand
The imaging process began by photographing the covers, high-quality images, with professional cameras, the cameras that were used to document the covers:

- DSLR Nikon D3000 Professional camera
- Kodak Easyshare C813 Zoom Digital Camera

to document the shape and size of the cover and the shapes engraved on the cover in principle.

During the photographic documentation process, I was able to reach simple principles based on which guiding instructions were developed to help the restorer and the notary in reaching the best reliable image in the documentation process.

I have monitored all the appropriate instructions in the form of a poster that is easy for the restorer to access for all the appropriate instructions and published it in my blog about restoration arts on March 16, 2018 (Ali, FOUNDATIONS OF DOCUMENTARY PHOTOGRAPHY, 2018), It was also used as a reference for documentary photography on the Facebook page of the Scandinavian Conservative Association Denmark (Nordisk Konservatorforbund Danmark)on May 29, 2018 (Ali, Nordisk Konservatorforbund Danmark, 2018)

Photographing is one of the most important means used by the conservator to document any archaeological work that is being restored, documentary photography is used for the following purposes:

- Documenting the damage before restoration and clarifying the restoration work carried out after the restoration.
- Protect the restorer from any accusation of damage in the absence of the purpose to be restored in custody.
- Protect the purpose to be repaired from any damage may increase it.
- Preserve the right of the Foundation to retain its property

Steps we should follow for Documentary photography:

- Arrange the staff around the item to be documented and isolate any area that can be confusing.
- Arrange the cadre geometrically using vertical and horizontal coordinate lines and avoid italics or curved lines.
- Avoid the tyranny of chromatic masses in the case of imaging blocks formative.
- Use neutral background either white or black or gray to separate the element and avoid double colors.
- Taking into account the rules of balance in the cadre, whether a single mass or a mass formation.
- Identify the centers of interest in the component and focus on them.

- Photography of the entire page all the details within the cadre should be clearly seen.
- In the case of the manuscript pages should be photocopied page by page.
- Focus on the elements within the page (places of various deterioration, seals, frames, gilding, ornamentation, signatures) and all that the restorer see is important for the purpose of documentation.
- Photography of important elements in the manuscript or book as cover, headband, and all what the restorer see is important for the purpose of documentation
- It is preferable to use the Normal or Tele lens in normal authentication cases and the Macro lens in the case of accurate, detailed documentation (when using the Macro lens prefer to use less focal distance of the lens Minimal Focal Distance).
- It is preferable to use the lens slot F-1.4 or F-2.8 and shutter speed between 250/1-160/1 and preferably ISO-400.
- It is preferable not to use the flash in photography, unless necessary, but not exceeding 16/1.
- If the element is photographed in its environment, attention should be paid to placing the element and preferably using the aerial perspective.

4foundations Of Documentary Photography

RTI Photography

The second stage in documentary photography was more accurate photography using the RTI technique to document the prominent and recessed shapes and the interpretation of the fine lines of the decorations engraved on the leather of the cover, some of which were obliterated by time and the frequent use, which was difficult to notice and document using ordinary photographic techniques. Some of the covers, in which it was not possible to see the details of the prominent and recessed lines, were photographed with the naked eye, using normal photographic techniques.

Calibration of camera parameters is an important step to use the RTI technology, and the camera parameters are the internal setup, camera calibration, and image sensor

estimating these parameters of camera according to (diaphragm / shutter speed/ white balance/ ISO light meter) make you able to use these parameters to correct for lens distortion and get the best (RAW file) to use for image post-processing.

5culturalheritageimaging.org/Technologies/RTI/

I calibrated the camera precisely to get the best picture and also used photographic targets to get good color balance in the pictures, such as the color checker, white balance card, and grayscale card.

- A color checker is a color chart with gradated colors that when used with software after you take the picture, this reference will set color balance file for a particular image set and all images captured thereafter.
- White balance is how warm or cool the overall colors in your photograph look, Smart camera is easily confused and can sometimes make the colors too warm or too cool, Most cameras default to the “Auto” white balance setting, which actually works pretty well, most of the time, a light grey card is designed to help photographers to adjust their exposure and white balance settings consistently by providing a reference point, This reference point will set a white balance, or color balance, point for a particular image set and all images captured thereafter.
- Exposure grey card is a middle grey reference, typically used together with a reflective light meter, as a way to produce consistent image exposure and/or color in film and photography. A grey card is a flat object of a neutral grey color that derives from a flat reflectance spectrum (Becki Robins, 2018)

Image processing

The goal of image processing is to look at the defects resulting from the document itself, and to look at the defects resulting from digitization and try to purify it to the extent that allows easy identification of all the elements that we want to document and in this field, there are several programs from which information can be extracted as Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI). (Nieuwenhuysen, 2010)

RTI (Reflectance Transformation Imaging) is a computational photographic method that captures a subject’s surface shape and color and enables the interactive re-lighting of the subject from any direction. RTI also permits the mathematical enhancement of the subject’s surface shape and color attributes. The enhancement functions of RTI reveal surface information that is not disclosed under direct empirical examination of the physical object. Today’s RTI software and related methodologies were constructed by a team of international developers (M. H. –. A. a. C. C. Becki Robins, 2018)

How does (RTI) works??

Mathematically, the direction that is perpendicular to the surface at any given location is represented by a vector (direction) called a normal.

Technically it is a vector that is perpendicular to the tangent plane at any point on the surface, as real surfaces are in 3D and this graphic is only 2-dimensional.

The mathematical description of the normal is saved per pixel, along with the RGB (red-green-blue) color information of a regular photograph. This ability to record efficiently the color and true 3D shape information is the source of RTI's documentary power (M. H. –. A. a. C. C. Becki Robins, 2018)

6surface normal direction

7RTI light Path

Image post processing

Post processing is the process of editing the data captured by a camera while taking the photo taken to enhance the image. The better the data captured from a camera to create the photo the better the enhancement possibility is.

Except for images captured using RTI technology, the rest of the images were directly processed using Adobe Photoshop CS5 version, which is the most powerful editing program available for image processing and improvement, also using the Adobe Camera Raw plugin with RAW files.

When the original images from the sequence have been acquired, post-processing is done to combine the images and ancillary data into the RTI image file.

I first reviewed the captured images for ease of use and added metadata to each one. Then I converted the camera raw files to JPEG format. JPEG images are used to create an RTI or to modify it in an image processing program, and you have used Adobe photoshop for image processing.

The RTI Builder app could have been used to collect data on the exact light direction of each image, which is calculated from the highlights of the reflective fields and in doing so, the reflective fields could be cropped from the images but for time constraints I was unable to perform the last step.

Image	Camera parameters	
<p data-bbox="250 1843 769 1906">8 cover photo using normal photography technique</p>	Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION
	Camera model	NIKON D3000
	F-stop	f/3.5
	Exposure time	1/40sec
	ISO speed	ISO-400
	Focal length	18mm
	Max aperture	3.6
	Flash mode	No flash compulsory
	35mm focal length	27

Image	Camera parameters	
<p data-bbox="289 919 732 951">9cover photo using RTI technique</p>	Camera make	EASTMAN KODAK COMPANY
	Camera model	KODAK EASYSHARE C813 ZOOM DIGITAL CAMERA
	F-stop	f/2.7
	Exposure time	1/9sec
	ISO speed	ISO-160
	Focal length	6mm
	Max aperture	2.86
	Flash mode	No flash compulsory
	35mm focal length	36

Transforming raster image into vector illustration

This is the last stage before the research stage behind the origin and history of the image details, and it is the most important stage that helped me clarify the important details that I searched behind by tracing the image using Adobe Illustrator CS5 program is to convert bitmap images (JPEG) into vector artwork. With this feature, I can easily base a new drawing on an existing art by tracing it.

Image	Illustration

10A picture from Ai program while tracing the cover details

11An explanation of how to re-trace the inscriptions on images using Adobe Illustrator

After this stage, I had clear data that facilitated the process of research and documentation

Chapter VI: Research and Documentation Process

Iconography

Before starting to explain the documentation process, an important term must be explained that explains the nature of many of the forms that we relied on in documentation, which is the term iconography.

Iconography, the science of identification, description, classification, and interpretation of symbols, themes, and subject matter in the visual arts. The term can also refer to the artist's use of this imagery in a particular work. The earliest iconographical studies, published in the 16th century, were catalogues of emblems and symbols collected from antique literature and translated into pictorial terms for the use of artists.

In 726 the Byzantine emperor Leo III took a public stand against the perceived worship of icons, and in 730 their use was officially prohibited. This opened a persecution of icon venerated that was severe in the reign of Leo's successor, Constantine V (741–775)

In 787, however, the empress Irene convoked the seventh ecumenical council at Nicaea at which Iconoclasm was condemned and the use of images was re-established. The Iconoclasts regained power in 814 after Leo V's accession, and the use of icons was again forbidden at a council in 815.

The most famous of this Iconology work was Cesare Ripa's *Iconologia* (1593). Extensive iconographical study did not begin in Europe until the 18th century, however, when, as a companion to archaeology, it consisted of the classification of subjects and motifs in ancient monuments. (Britannica, 1998)

Manuscripts Indexing data

Manuscript Name	Author	Copyist	Subject	Copying Year	Production Year
Canonicals	Emmanuel Malaxus	George Armenipolos	Ecclesiastical law	1708 AD	1706 AD
Summary and exegesis of the holy ecclesiastical canon	Ioannis Zonaras	Unknown	Ecclesiastical law	15th century	Unknown
Gospel's Reading Guide	The Four preachers	Georgios Mikhaiel Sinsiel	Ecclesiastical readings	1709 AD	1st century
Explanation of Theophilios on the book of soul of Aristotle	Monk Ioakim Bistis	Unknown	Philosophy	Unknown	1645 AD

Canonicals

Dates back to 1706 AD written by St.Emmanuel Malaxus, transcribed on 1708 AD by. St.George Armenipolos on paper, full-bound brown leather binding on paste boards with geometric and floral ornaments of both covers, in the middle of both covers, an engraved medallion, the medallion on the upper board illustrates a shape of a crucified man and other shapes, the one the lower board illustrates a lady holding a child.

Canonicals Meaning

Canonicals or Canon law has been set by the Christian Church and which, in virtually all places, is not binding upon citizens except to the extent of exposure to ostracization by Church institutions and members and has virtually no recognition in the judicial system.

Canon law covers such things as the process of religious service, criteria for baptism, funerals, prohibited conduct, church property, and internal boards which have jurisdiction over Church matters also known as ecclesiastical law. (Daube, 2009)

12the lower board with illustration of a lady holding a child

Camera parameters	
Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION
Camera model	NIKON D3000
F-stop	f/4.8
Exposure time	1/15sec
ISO speed	ISO-400
Focal length	38mm
Max aperture	4.5
Flash mode	No flash compulsory
35mm focal length	57

13the upper board with illustration a shape of a crucified man and other shapes

Camera parameters	
Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION
Camera model	NIKON D3000
F-stop	f/3.8
Exposure time	1/40sec
ISO speed	ISO-400
Focal length	24mm
Max aperture	4.5
Flash mode	No flash compulsory
35mm focal length	36

Summary and exegesis of the holy ecclesiastical canon

Dates to 12th century, written by st. Loannis Zonaras; and transcribed on 15th century, by various writers The manuscript is full bound in European style, in reddish brown leather with ornaments on both sides, the upper board the upper board contains an engraved medallion also illustrates a shape of a crucified man and other shapes, the lower board illustrates vertical line of floral ornaments.

	Camera parameters	
Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION	
Camera model	NIKON D3000	
F-stop	f/3.8	
Exposure time	1/40sec	
ISO speed	ISO-400	
Focal length	24mm	
aperture	4.5	
Flash mode	No flash compulsory	
35mm focal length	36	

upper board with illustration a shape of a crucified man and other shapes

15 the lower board illustrates a Vertical line of Floral ornaments.

Camera parameters	
Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION
Camera model	NIKON D3000
F-stop	f/3.8
Exposure time	1/50sec
ISO speed	ISO-800
Focal length	22mm
aperture	3.9
Flash mode	No flash compulsory
35mm focal length	33

Illustration of central medallions

The two aforementioned manuscripts share a similarity to the medallion engraved in the center of the cover. The following illustrations show the details of each.

16 Summary and exegesis of the holy ecclesiastical canon central medallion on the left and illustration of the medallion on the right

17 canonical central medallion on the left and illustration of the medallion on the right

Interpretation Of the Engraved Iconography

The Crucifixion is one of the famous symbols of the Greek Orthodox, I want to point out some obvious features. First, it is clear that the person leading the middle of the inscription and hanging on the cross is Jesus Christ, and he appears with the almost same characteristics in the two icons. (Beck, 2008)

then, we tend to see Mary and the women to the left of the cross. Mary is sometimes distinguished as the only woman with a halo around her head. (Beck, 2008)

18summary and exegesis Mary with another woman

19Canonicals Mary stand alone

the men on the other side of the cross are John, also with a halo, and the Centurion who confesses that “Surely this was the Son of God.” John may also appear alone or accompanied by the centurion, and the is centurion a Roman soldier who pierced Jesus in his side with a lance and who in medieval and some modern Christian traditions is described as a convert to Christianity. (Beck, 2008)

20summary and exegesis John with the centurion

21Canonicals John stand alone

In the background we see the city walls and gates of Jerusalem. This depicts Jesus being crucified “outside the gate,” a reference to the scapegoat ritual during the Day of Atonement where the scapegoat carries the sins of the people “outside the camp.”

One interesting feature in some icons is showing the sun and moon. The sun is generally darkened. The moon is colored red. These symbols echo this passage in Scripture. (The sun turned black like sackcloth made of goat hair, the whole moon turned blood red).

the most interesting feature of these icons as it is non-obvious and is a theological addition to the icon. If you look at the base of the cross you see a skull and perhaps even some bones.

The bible says that Jesus was crucified at a place called Golgotha, the place of the skull. In church tradition the place of the skull was the burial site of Adam. Symbolically, therefore, Jesus is being crucified directly over Adam’s tomb. In the icons we can see this tomb being cracked open which exposes Adam’s skull and bones.

Adam’s skull is a strong Orthodox notion that what was defeated at the cross was death. This is the same emphasis that leads the Orthodox to focus on the harrowing of hell at Easter. (Beck, 2008)

22 18th century iconography represents the crucifixion features (Beck, 2008)

Inscriptions in Orthodox Iconography

We notice the presence of inscriptions in the icons on the background and above the cross written in close shapes, as if they were abbreviations for certain words.

23The forms of inscriptions that appeared in the icons

Also, letters (**INBI**) appeared directly above the head of Christ, and their position did not change

Icon inscriptions are symbols and acronyms accepted in the Russian Orthodox icon-painting tradition. Inscriptions can be made both in Church Slavonic and in Greek language. In these inscriptions, contracture is widely used for “shrinking”, which is writing a reduced form of a word with the help of its first and last letters. Above such words, a special symbol called titlo (˘) is written. (BibleWalks.com, 2014)

Inscription	Interpretation
“IC-XC NI-KA”	Jesus Christ conquers
“MP ΘC”	Mother of God
“O ωN”	He Who is”, refers to God or his messenger.
“INBI”	Jesus of Nazareth King of the Jews

Conclusion

After analyzing all those symbols and references previously mentioned on the manuscripts and linking them to the original subject of the manuscript, we understand why the icon of the crucifixion was chosen to represent the title of ecclesiastical canons away from the judicial system to cover the process of religious service, and baptism criteria

Because the icon of the crucifixion represents the injustice done to Christ and his followers in light of the laws of the state, which is what prompted the church to enact its own law

Gospels Reading guide

Dates to 1st century by written by the four missionaries, copied at 1709 AD by. St. Georgious Sinsel on paper, full-bound brown leather binding on wood boards with geometric and floral ornaments of both covers, in the middle of both covers, an engraved medallion, the medallion on the upper board illustrates a shape of man holding a sword, the one n the lower board illustrates a lady holding a child.

Gospels Reading guide meaning

The Gospel in Christian liturgy refers to a reading from the Gospels used during various religious services, including Mass or Divine Liturgy (Eucharist). In many Christian churches, all present stand when a passage from one of the Gospels is read publicly and sit when a passage from a different part of the Bible is read. The reading of the Gospels, often contained in a liturgical edition containing only the four Gospels, is traditionally done by a minister, priest, or deacon, and in many traditions the Gospel Book is brought into the midst of the congregation to be read.

<p>24the upper board illustrates a shape of man holding a sword</p>	Camera parameters	
	Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION
	Camera model	NIKON D3000
	F-stop	f/3.8
	Exposure time	1/50sec
	ISO speed	ISO-800
	Focal length	22mm
	Max aperture	3.9
	Flash mode	No flash Compulsory
	35 mm focal lens	28

25the upper board illustrates a shape of a lady holding child

Camera parameters	
Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION
Camera model	NIKON D3000
F-stop	f/3.5
Exposure time	1/25sec
ISO speed	ISO-400
Focal length	28mm
Max aperture	3.6
Flash mode	No flash Compulsory
35 mm focal lens	28

Illustration of central medallions

The manuscripts here also share a similarity to the medallion engraved in the centre of the cover of the lower board of Canonicals Manuscript. The following illustrations show the details of each.

26 Upper board central medallion on the left and illustration of the medallion on the right

27 lower board central medallion on the left and illustration of the medallion on the right

Interpretation Of the Engraved Iconography

Virgin and the child

The Blessed Virgin Mary has been one of the major subjects of Christian Art, Catholic Art and Western Art for many centuries. Literally hundreds of thousands of pieces of Marian art in the Orthodox Church covering a range of Marian artistic topics have been produced, from masters such as Michelangelo and Botticelli to humble peasant artists, the most famous icons in byzantine of virgin marry baby Jesus are (Virgin eleusa, Virgin Orans, Virgin hodegetria) (D'Ancona, (1957))

Virgin eleusa

The Eleusa (tenderness or showing mercy) is a type of depiction of the Virgin Mary in icons in which the infant Jesus Christ is nestled against her cheek. In the Western church the type is often known as the Virgin of Tenderness. (Evans, 2004)

28sample for virgin Eleusa iconography

Virgin Orans

The Icon of Our Lady of the Sign is the term for a particular type of icon of the Theotokos (Virgin Mary), facing the viewer directly, depicted either full length or half, with her hands raised in the orans position, and with the image of the Child Jesus depicted within a round aureole upon her breast. The Virgin's solemn and static posture, the characteristic folds of her garments, and her pensive expression indicate the design was strongly influenced by Byzantine art. (Evans, 2004)

29sample for virgin Oranse iconography

Virgin Hodegetria

A Hodegetria literally "She who shows the Way" Virgin Hodegetria, is an iconographic depiction of (Virgin Mary) holding the Child Jesus at her side while pointing to Him as the

source of salvation for mankind. In the Western Church this type of icon is sometimes called Our Lady of the Way. (Evans, 2004)

30sample for virgin Hodegetria iconography

From a visual observation of the technical features of each of the three icons and comparing them with the technical features on the medal on the cover, we find that the icon is the lady who shows the Way Virgin Hodegetria.

Saint Michael the Archangel

Saint Michael the Archangel" Oriental and Eastern Orthodox Christians refer to him as the "Taxiarch Archangel Michael" or simply "Archangel Michael".

Saint Michael symbolizes the victory of good over evil, and he has been widely represented in art through the ages. Depictions of Saint Michael often portray the scene where Satan, or the fallen angels, are helpless below the sword or spear of a triumphant Saint Michael.

He holds a round object in his left-hand signifying God as the true ruler of the world. The trumpet in his right hand signifies Michael as the announcer for the second coming of Jesus Christ during the final judgment. (Gonzalez) (D'Ancona, (1957))

31 iconography represents Michel the archangel

Conclusion

After analyzing all those symbols and references already mentioned on the two manuscript icons and linking them to the original theme of how to read sacred gospels, we understand why the Virgin Icon carrying the child in this manner is chosen to represent the guide that lights the way, which is somehow the same as the title of the manuscript.

The artist emphasizes the authority and strength of faith in choosing the icon of St. Michael, the most powerful of the angels, as if it were a symbol of protection for the content of the manuscript.

The Book of soul of Aristotle

The manuscript transcribed in 1645 CE, by Monk Lokim Bistis, bound in European style, in reddish brown leather with ornaments on both sides, the upper board contains an engraved medallion also illustrates a shape of a man confronts a woman, the lower board illustrates vertical line of floral ornaments.

The book of soul is a major treatise written by Aristotle c.350 B.C. Although its topic is the soul, it is not about spirituality but rather a work in what might best be described as biopsychology, a description of the subject of psychology within a biological framework. (Aristotle, 2019)

	Camera parameters	
Camera make	NIKON CORPORATION	
Camera model	NIKON D3000	
F-stop	f/3.5	
Exposure time	1/40sec	
ISO speed	ISO-400	
Focal length	18mm	
Max aperture	3.6	
Flash mode	No flash compulsory	
35mm focal length	27	

32the lower board with illustration of a lady confronts a man

Illustration of central medallion

33central medallion on the left and illustration of the medallion on the right

Interpretation Of the Engraved Iconography

The Annunciation

The Annunciation has been a key topic in Christian art in general, as well as in Marian art in the Catholic Church, particularly during the Middle Ages and Renaissance. A work of art depicting the Annunciation is sometimes itself called an Annunciation. (Gorlinski, 2010)

Above the head of the Virgin and the angel standing in front of her is his vase, from which three flowers emerge, after research, it turned out to be the Columbian flower

Thought by some to look like a dove, the columbine is a symbol of the Holy Spirit. The name comes from the Latin Columba, which means "dove."

The text written above the vase was also translated from the Latin language, and the translation of the sentence "He Did" refers to God's command to breathe the soul of Jesus Christ into the womb of Lady Mary. (David, 2018)

34 columbine flowers

δΛΛΤΖΒΕΨΕ

35latin text translated into English

Conclusion

The choice of the Annunciation icon was the greatest indication of the subject of the manuscript, which is a description of the subject of psychology in a biological framework, as the the Annunciation carries the two connotations, spiritual one with the presence of the holy spirit with a sacred divine order by placing a soul inside a soul

And the biological indication of the presence of a real child inside the body of Virgin Mary

Chapter V: Conclusion

Icons and inscriptions engraved on the covers of manuscripts may carry connotations and symbols that contribute to determining the date and type of subject matter of the content of the manuscript. The manuscript cover alone may prove the extent of the manuscript's originality or not.

In many cases, high-quality covers and inscriptions come, and we find the content is poor and not completely consistent with the cover, and here the restorer or indexer must stop and study the inscriptions and decorations on the cover and compare the history of each inscription with the history and content of the manuscript, and this may prove manipulation or Theft or even a previous restoration error that the manuscript has gone through.

Chapter IV: Recommendation

I recommend the next stage of the research is to complete the documentation of the rest of the manuscripts of the group to provide an accurate historic archive about manuscripts covers they can be used to maintain information about the production, collection, ownership, and use of manuscripts and information about the date of manuscript and date of the cover itself.

I also recommend to attach the information extracted from documenting the covers to the manuscripts after restoration, whether to be displayed on museum label, or on saving boxes of manuscripts.

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توثيق التجليد الزخرفى لتأريخ مخطوطات العصور الوسطى

إعداد

داليا على السيد

رسالة علمية مقدمة الى

الجامعة المصرية اليابانية للعلوم والتكنولوجيا

كاستيفاء جزئي لمتطلبات الحصول على درجة الماجستير فى علوم التراث (مهنى)

فى تخصص

علوم التراث و إدارة المتاحف

يوليو 2021

توثيق التجليد الزخرفى لتأريخ مخطوطات العصور الوسطى

مقدم من

داليا على السيد

للحصول على درجة الماجستير فى علوم التراث (مهنى)

فى

برنامج علوم التراث و ادارة المتاحف

المرشد الأكاديمى

الاسم:	جهة العمل	التوقيع
1. دكتور / سيد حميده	استاذ علوم التراث و الترميم المعمارى بالجامعه المصريه اليابانيه للعلوم و التكنولوجيا

لجنة المناقشة والحكم

الاسم:	جهة العمل	التوقيع
1. دكتور / سيد حميده	استاذ علوم التراث و الترميم المعمارى بالجامعه المصريه اليابانيه للعلوم و التكنولوجيا
2. دكتور / عائشه عبدالعال	استاذ علوم التراث
3. دكتور / تاكاو كيكوتشى	أستاذ علم الآثار والتاريخ القديم بالجامعه المصريه اليابانيه للعلم و التكنولوجيا

ملخص المشروع باللغة العربية

كانت الحاجة إلى حماية الممتلكات الثقافية من التلف والضياع والسرقة والجرائم ضد الإنسانية بمثابة حافز لتطوير ممارسات التوثيق و فى اطار توثيق المخطوطات تعد مخطوطات العصور الوسطى من بين أكثر مجالات التوثيق إثارة للاهتمام.

توفر هذه الحقبة نافذة على التاريخ من القرن الخامس إلى أوائل القرن السادس عشر ، لكن لسوء الحظ ، بينما تمت دراسة المخطوطات نفسها ، تمت الإشارة إلى الأغلفة بشكل وجيز فقط و حين كان يتم البحث عن معلومات لتوثيق الغلاف ف اغلب الاحيان يكون الغلاف تم استبداله بجديد و تعرض الاصل للتلف او الفقدان.

لذلك يناقش البحث كيفية وضع أساس لتوثيق الأيقونات والنقوش المحفورة على أغلفة المخطوطات التي قد تحمل دلالات ورموز تساهم في تحديد تاريخ ونوع موضوع محتوى المخطوطة.